

Developing mathematics education promoting equity and inclusion: Is it possible?

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This paper is a discussion of the possibility to develop an inclusive and equitable mathematics education in primary school based on success factors found in prior research. The overall goal is to develop a model for education and to develop an approach where sociopolitical and pedagogical issues are core. The study contributes to this important and challenging task by building on earlier research from different fields of relevance, generating a model for sustainable development of mathematics education, and at the same time, deriving from and anchoring the model in teachers and students' experiences of everyday life in the mathematics classroom.

Introduction

The Swedish school and mathematics education's ideal of a school for all has been heavily challenged in the last decade as segregation and inequalities have been enhanced at the same time as knowledge has decreased in the subject of mathematics. A struggle for both society, research and practice is to include an agenda of equity and inclusion in mathematics education (Roos, 2019; Bagger, 2017), even though these issues are central for every student learning in mathematics (Atweh, 2011). The struggle has been shown in research as complexity and multiple issues regarding equity and inclusion have been explained (Kollosche et al., 2019). Hence, the explanations to better understand inclusion and equity are found in very different fields. Examples are research on socioeconomics (e.g., Thien, 2016), gender (e.g., Leder & Forgasz, 2008), ethnicity (e.g., Martin, 2019) cultural background (e.g., Meaney, Edmonds-Wathen, McMurchy-Pilkington & Trinick, 2016), language (e.g., Planas, Morgan & Schütte, 2018), disability (e.g., Tan, Lambert, Padilla & Wieman, 2019), ability (e.g., Leikin, 2011), curriculum (e.g., Askew, 2015), educational approaches (e.g., Kollosche et al., 2019), and assessment (e.g., Bagger, 2017). All these fields aim at creating a mathematics education for optimal opportunities to learn, though rather separate from each other. Out of this separate and multitudinous base of knowledge, success factors regarding sociopolitical and pedagogical issues can be retrieved. Thereafter these issues can be applied to develop an approach in mathematics education that promotes equity and inclusion. Following, this paper aims to investigate the possibility of a project focusing on promoting equity and inclusion in mathematics education in primary school in a Swedish context. This

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is done by presenting the core ideas behind a practice-based project with the aim to support the development of mathematics education which promotes equity and inclusion in the classroom. The result will be two-fold: to develop a model for education and to develop an approach where sociopolitical and pedagogical issues are core. The tentative research questions of the project are:

- What are already identified success factors on societal and classroom levels for equity and inclusion in education?
- How can this theoretically build a foundation for developing a model for inclusive mathematics education?
- How can criteria for equity and inclusion be developed in collaboration with teachers and students?
- How is the relation between this inclusive mathematics education in primary school and student's view of equity and inclusion?

Equity and inclusion in mathematics education

The notions of equity and inclusion are both complex and not always particularly defined in mathematics education research (Bagger, 2017; Roos, 2019). Although, they are frequently used in order to highlight the importance to consider every student's learning on both individual- and societal level (see for instance Askew, 2015). We define inclusion as processes of participation in learning and teaching in mathematics (Roos, 2019). We draw on Cobb and Hodge (2007) in our understanding of equity as something that “contributes to student empowerment, development, and in turn, their ability and agency to learn” (p. 71, Bagger, 2017). Consequently, we claim that inclusive and equitable mathematics education is an education that strives for every student's opportunity to participate in learning processes and develop the ability and agency to learn. Hence, education that considers equity and inclusion simultaneously. Research regarding educational quality and equity is complex and questions of who has access, or possibilities to get access are highlighted (e.g., Askew, 2015). Here, not only issues of what is happening within the mathematics classroom are at stake, but also issues of power and democracy in society (Halai, Mushaffar & Valero, 2016). This makes the learning of the individual student influenced by structures in society and continuous processes of in(ex)clusion is present (Halai, Mushaffar & Valero, 2016).

Bridging equity, inclusion and mathematics teaching – a reflection

In this future study both mathematics teaching and learning as well as students' own view of equity and inclusion needs to be studied at an individual and classroom level. Though, it also has to be understood and developed from a societal perspective foregrounding issues of power and democracy. To be able to, firstly develop a mathematics education based on success factors both on societal and classroom level, and secondly, investigate the relationship between success factors for equal and inclusive mathematics education and student's view of equity and inclusion, there needs to be a bridge between classroom and

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societal issues. Also, there is a need to be attentive to power relations in the recontextualisation, acquisition and transmission of knowledge between research and practice (see Bernstein, 2003). Therefore, we build our framework on Bernstein's (1999) theories of the pedagogical device and vertical and horizontal discourses in education. Bernstein states that:

The shift in equity from equality ('of opportunity') to recognition of diversity (of voice) may well be responsible for the colonisation of vertical discourse [knowledge retrieved from research] or the appropriation by vertical discourse of horizontal discourse [knowledge retrieved from practice] (Bernstein, 1999, p. 169).

Challenges for the future study

One challenge for this future study will be to explicitly find and investigate both research regarding societal issues on equity and inclusion, as well as classroom issues within different research paradigms of relevance. Another challenge is to be able to create a collaboration with teachers and students generating data consisting of observations and interviews with teachers and students as well as quantitative measures of knowledge development. In order to not colonise horizontal discourse (see Bernstein, 1999) while investigating prior research and researching with teachers and students important questions to ask are: What factor is important to start with? How (if possible) do different factors connect? How do the factors work in relation to specific cultures, contexts, and students? Is it possible to reconsider all factors identified when creating inclusive mathematics education?

The overall aim and hope for this future study is to contribute with a model for supporting the development of mathematics education that promotes equity and inclusion. The study will take both sociopolitical and pedagogical aspects into consideration and aims at shedding light not only on successful mathematics teaching but also on the students' part and perspective in such teaching.

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